

Politics and Rights Review

Healing Divides: The Power of Recognition in Social Justice

Michèle Lamont's *Seeing Others* offers a compelling examination of how recognizing the humanity and worth of every individual can bridge societal divides and foster inclusivity.

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— Protestors in the Fight for 15 movement demand recognition for their hard work and fair wages, advocating for a \$15 per hour minimum wage.

Michèle Lamont's *Seeing Others: How Recognition Works and How It Can Heal a Divided World* is a profound exploration of the power of recognition in bridging societal divides. Serving as a blueprint for fostering a more inclusive and equitable society, the book combines rigorous research with compelling narratives to illustrate how recognizing the humanity and worth of every individual can transform communities and heal social fractures.

Lamont addresses persistent inequalities deeply rooted in a lack of **recognition and respect for diverse groups**. By exploring the psychological and social dimensions of marginalization, the book offers a **comprehensive view of how**

recognition—or the lack thereof—shapes our identities and interactions.

Understanding the quest for dignity is essential for making sense of discontent on both sides of the ideological aisle.

— Michèle Lamont

One of the aspects that makes *Seeing Others* particularly engaging is **Lamont's ability to seamlessly weave personal stories with empirical data**. This approach not only makes the book accessible to a broader audience but also underscores the real-world implications of her theories.

Readers are invited to reflect on their own roles within these social structures and consider how they might contribute to a more inclusive society. Lamont's call to action is clear: **to create lasting change, we must begin by changing the way we see and value each other**.

Mechanisms of Privilege and Exclusion

In her detailed examination of the elite perspective, Michèle Lamont reveals how those at the top of the social hierarchy maintain their privileged positions through mechanisms of exclusion. She explores the symbolic and material barriers that elites build to protect their status, **offering a critical lens on the cultural and social practices that sustain inequality**.

The boundary organized around the American dream is also the moral boundary that structures the class system.

— Michèle Lamont

Lamont argues that these practices are **not merely about wealth but about a deeper sense of moral worth and entitlement** that elites claim for themselves. She meticulously dissects the narratives that elites use to justify their positions, showing how they frame their success as a result of hard work and superior abilities while implicitly or explicitly devaluing those who do not share their privileges.

Furthermore, Lamont illustrates how these narratives perpetuate social inequalities, making it clear that the **recognition of one's worth is deeply intertwined with social and economic power.**

In this way, the author offers a **powerful critique of the meritocratic myth** that suggests anyone can succeed with enough effort, highlighting how this narrative ignores structural barriers and systemic inequalities.

—— Damian Lillard, star player for the Portland Trail Blazers, stands in solidarity at a Black Lives Matter march in Portland, demanding recognition for the ongoing struggle against racial injustice and systemic inequality. Photo by Matthew Roth.

Lamont calls for a re-evaluation of these narratives, suggesting that **true meritocracy can only be achieved through a more equitable distribution of recognition and resources.** She also criticizes the physical separation between classes in neighborhoods, workplaces, and schools, noting that fewer Americans today are in contact with people from other income groups compared to the 1970s. This physical separation **exacerbates social divisions and perpetuates misunderstandings and prejudices.**

By providing insights into the mindset and strategies of the elite, Lamont helps readers understand the broader social dynamics at play. This understanding is crucial for anyone interested in social justice, as **it sheds light on the often-invisible mechanisms that perpetuate inequality**. The detailed examples and empirical data she provides make a compelling case for why we need to challenge and change these entrenched systems of exclusion.

The Struggles of the Marginalized: Voices from Below

Turning her focus to the experiences of the working class and marginalized groups, Michèle Lamont paints a vivid picture of the struggles faced by those at the lower end of the social spectrum. **Her work serves as a sobering reminder of the real human costs of economic policies and social attitudes that devalue certain groups.**

Lamont explores the psychological and social impacts of poverty and marginalization, showing how these experiences erode individuals' sense of self-worth and belonging.

Welfare recipients still face intense stigmatization in America.

— Michèle Lamont

The book highlights **the systemic nature of these challenges**, pointing out how neoliberal economic policies have exacerbated inequalities and left many people struggling to meet their basic needs.

Lamont provides a detailed account of how these policies have led to declining wages, job insecurity, and the dismantling of social safety nets. This point is particularly poignant as **it captures the voices and stories of individuals who have been left behind by the economic shifts of recent decades.**

Lamont's ability to humanize statistics and data stands out. She introduces readers to the personal stories of those affected by these policies, making their struggles and resilience tangible. This approach fosters empathy and underscores the urgency of addressing these issues. Lamont's argument is clear: to create a more just society, **we must recognize and value the contributions and dignity of all individuals**, regardless of their economic status.

Towards Inclusivity: A Path Forward

In addressing the pervasive exclusion present in modern society, Michèle Lamont offers a roadmap for fostering a more inclusive world. She critiques the individualistic solutions often proposed, such as self-help and personal resilience,

arguing that **these approaches fail to address the structural roots of exclusion**. Instead, Lamont advocates for a comprehensive strategy that includes economic reforms, policy changes, and, crucially, a shift in societal narratives about worth and belonging.

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Political or institutional reforms will never be sufficient to produce the change we need unless we are also able to change our narratives.

— Michèle Lamont

Stressing the importance of changing hearts and minds alongside implementing policy reforms, the author argues that **without addressing the cultural and social narratives that justify exclusion, any policy changes are likely to be superficial and short-lived**. The book calls for a broadening of our collective understanding of who belongs and deserves recognition, emphasizing that true inclusivity requires both systemic and cultural change.

—— Participants at a Pride parade hold signs reading 'Love is a Human Right,' seeking recognition for LGBTQ+ rights. Photo by Ian Taylor.

The book also calls for confronting the stereotypes used to justify spatial segregation as well as the narratives that lead some to perceive other groups as less worthy. **Narratives are central to her argument.** She defines narratives as more than just stories: “*they are perspectives about society and social relations that allow people to make sense of the world*” (p. 51).

Narratives have power. They shape how we describe reality to ourselves and to others, encompassing everything from our identities and experiences to our social environments and groups. When economists and behavioral scientists disregard narratives, they overlook aspects that are central to our reality.

We can push simultaneously for greater recognition *and* greater material equality.

—— Michèle Lamont

The book examines recognition not only from a political perspective but also from cultural, social, and psychological perspectives.

It explores how social consensus ensures political rights for different groups, such as the right to vote, representation, and access to public resources.

However, it also highlights the importance of culture to individuals and groups, and examines how marginalization, intolerance, and the denial of dignity affect various aspects of life, beginning with psychological well-being.

In this way, Lamont provides **a holistic approach to tackling exclusion.** Her recommendations are grounded in a deep understanding of the complexities of social change, acknowledging that while economic policies are vital, they must be accompanied by efforts to transform societal values and perceptions. **This dual approach is essential for creating a lasting and meaningful impact.**

Recognition Chains as Catalysts for Change

Michèle Lamont examines the concept of **recognition chains as a crucial mechanism for promoting inclusive cultural agendas and driving social change**. These chains consist of networks of actors and organizations that work collaboratively to create and disseminate new narratives that encourage equity and respect.

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Recognition is far more than the work of a self-serving progressive elite : it requires collaboration between many people who work toward some form of social change.

— Michèle Lamont

Recognition chains operate by connecting creators, critics, cultural institutions, foundations, and digital platforms, facilitating the spread of inclusive messages through various forms of art and media. These actors work together to reshape public perceptions and promote a more just representation of marginalized groups.

—— Cornel West, a prominent public intellectual and philosopher, passionately speaking at an anti-Trump protest in Union Square on October 19, 2019. Photo By Victoria Pickering (CC BY-NC-ND).

The significance of recognition chains lies in **their ability to change hearts and minds by providing visibility and dignity to underrepresented communities**. By broadening the range of available narratives, these chains help bridge recognition gaps, allowing people to see themselves and others in a fuller, more human light.

Recognition chains play a vital role in social change. By influencing how cultural and social identities are understood and valued, these chains can transform power structures and advance social justice. Collaboration across different sectors, including art, philanthropy, academia, and technology, is essential for amplifying the impact of these narratives and achieving lasting change.

Transforming Narratives: Strategies for Social Justice and Inclusion

Michèle Lamont's book illustrates that strategies for transforming cultural narratives and promoting social justice involve **varied and unique approaches by change agents from diverse fields**. In Hollywood, comedians, actors, directors, and producers challenge stereotypes and create nuanced representations of marginalized groups. These strategies include:

- ☑ **Reflecting Reality:** Telling stories that avoid reinforcing stereotypes and stay true to the realities of life for non-dominant groups. A notable example of this is the work of W. Kamau Bell and Joey Soloway, who focus on expanding society's understanding of marginalized groups by accurately depicting their lives.
- ☑ **Emotional Modulation:** Appealing to audiences' emotions to change their perceptions of a certain group. Tanya Saracho's show *Vida* is a powerful instance of this strategy, as it fosters empathy by highlighting both the joys and struggles of queer life and the brutal homophobia prevalent in society.
- ☑ **The Trojan Horse:** Subtly including social messages in seemingly neutral entertainment. A prime example is *Shameless*, a Showtime series that tells the story of a family living in poverty, exposing viewers to the stark realities of the American healthcare system and issues related to addiction and health.
- ☑ **See It to Be It:** Proactively opening career pathways in creative industries for members of marginalized groups. Cristela Alonzo exemplifies this approach by using her platform to mentor and create opportunities for new writers and comics, particularly from Latinx backgrounds. Her commitment to mentorship and support is an integral part of this strategy, aiming to empower others to create their own projects and succeed in the industry.

These efforts are crucial for shifting public perceptions and expanding recognition. By presenting marginalized groups in a humanized and relatable manner, change agents dismantle harmful stereotypes and foster a culture of inclusion. Activists and organizations also play a pivotal role by using social media, news outlets, and grassroots campaigns to advocate for equity. They mobilize communities, influence policy, and create new frameworks for understanding systemic inequalities.

Collectively, these change agents across various sectors drive social change by **reshaping cultural narratives and promoting recognition**, helping to create a more inclusive and just society. Their diverse strategies and collaborative actions are essential for transformative change.

Gen Z: Pioneers of Social Change

The book illuminates how Gen Z is redefining social change by **combining neoliberal ideals with a strong emphasis on recognition, mental health, and community improvement**. Lamont highlights how these young individuals navigate the pressures of achieving professional success while championing inclusivity and equity for all.

—— During the interviews in Lamont's research, students most often mentioned environmentalist Greta Thunberg as an influence that inspired them. Photo by European Parliament.

Lamont argues that this generation values authenticity and well-being, **often prioritizing personal balance over the relentless pursuit of success.** Their commitment to social justice is evident in their widespread support for movements like Black Lives Matter, emphasizing the importance of recognition and dignity for marginalized groups. They believe that everyone, regardless of background, deserves respect and opportunities.

Lamont also highlights that Gen Z's activism is driven by a sense of urgency to address systemic inequalities and environmental issues. **Drawing inspiration from figures like Greta Thunberg and Bernie Sanders, they are highly critical of the materialism and consumerism that define the traditional American dream.** Instead, they advocate for sustainable living and meaningful contributions to society.

Today's youth are demanding respect for a wider range of groups with historically stigmatized identities.

—— *Michèle Lamont*

Through the testimonies included in her book, **Lamont gives voice to these young individuals, not merely discussing their claims and needs, but allowing them to speak for themselves.** This approach enriches her analysis and provides an authentic representation of their perspectives and aspirations.

Despite their challenges, including economic uncertainty and mental health struggles, Gen Z remains hopeful. Lamont underscores their determination to create a more inclusive and equitable world, leveraging their collective power and innovative thinking to drive change. **Their focus on community and solidarity represents a significant shift from individualistic ideals,** highlighting the transformative potential of their generation. Lamont's insights provide a valuable perspective on the future of social activism and the evolving values of today's youth.

Building an Inclusive Society: Strategies for Broader Recognition

Seeing others offers insightful solutions for building an inclusive society by promoting broader recognition and **transforming how we view marginalized groups.** Lamont emphasizes the importance of diverse strategies,

including the need for expansive narratives that celebrate various standards of worth beyond neoliberal ideals, such as spirituality, morality, altruism, creativity, and civic-mindedness.

Institutions play a crucial role in fostering recognition and dignity. Employers can support work/family balance through policies like family leave and flex time, demonstrating that employees' personal lives matter. This approach reduces absenteeism and increases job satisfaction, showing the positive impact of recognizing employees' multifaceted roles.

The quest for recognition can bring together those at the extreme poles of American politics.

— Michèle Lamont

Individuals also play a central role in promoting inclusion by cultivating diverse relationships, living in integrated neighborhoods, and valuing a wide range of traits like creativity and altruism. **This daily practice of broadening recognition helps dismantle harmful stereotypes and fosters a culture of inclusion.**

The importance of new narratives in reducing stigma and enhancing dignity is emphasized through various examples. For instance, the destigmatization of individuals living with HIV/AIDS was significantly aided by credible support from experts and public figures. On the other hand, **attempts to combat fat-shaming have encountered more resistance**, demonstrating the critical need for widespread support in efforts to reduce stigma.

American schools can do more to teach multicultural values.

— Michèle Lamont

Legal and organizational policies significantly influence recognition. For example, inclusive school policies regarding natural hairstyles for Black girls can boost self-esteem and academic performance. Lawmakers and policy experts must consider the messaging power of their decisions, ensuring that they promote dignity and inclusion.

Lamont's vision for an inclusive society **combines individual actions, institutional policies, and new narratives to create transformative change**. She posits that although these ideals may appear ambitious, they are crucial for building a future where everyone is recognized and valued.

Avenues for Future Research

Seeing Others offers profound insights into the mechanisms of recognition and its impact on social cohesion and human well-being. Simultaneously, **it opens several intriguing questions and potential areas for further exploration** that could deepen our understanding of recognition and its broader implications.

The book explores cultural differences in recognition practices, focusing primarily on the American context, with comparative references to the French context and mentions of other cultures. Expanding this research internationally would be beneficial. **Cross-cultural research could provide valuable insights into what is valued in different contexts**. Different cultures have varying needs regarding what should be recognized and valued.

A more extensive comparative analysis across a broader range of countries could uncover diverse strategies for fostering recognition and solidarity. Understanding how different cultures approach recognition could reveal global best practices and innovative strategies that can be adapted across various contexts.

Ordinary people can work to reduce stigma of marginalized groups.

— Michèle Lamont

The role of digital platforms and social media in shaping and disseminating narratives of recognition is another promising area for exploration. While Lamont addresses the growing popularity of these platforms and their role in recognition chains, a deeper exploration into these digital realms could yield valuable insights. Understanding **how algorithms and online communities contribute to or detract from efforts to promote dignity and inclusivity** is crucial.

Furthermore, **the sustainability of current recognition practices raises important questions**. As societal attitudes evolve, what mechanisms can ensure that inclusive narratives remain resilient against backlash or complacency? Examining historical case studies of social movements that have experienced both successes and setbacks could provide valuable lessons on maintaining momentum in the fight for recognition and justice.

Hope has clear implications for social change.

— Michèle Lamont

Exploring the nuanced role of recognition chains within different political ideologies also presents fertile ground for research.

While Lamont examines how both progressive and conservative movements utilize recognition chains, **her findings open new avenues for analyzing the comparative strategies and outcomes in these differing contexts**, promising to yield fascinating insights into the dynamics of social change.

Another aspect that warrants exploration is Lamont's suggestion that people can choose to reside in more integrated neighborhoods and enroll their children in more diverse schools. She argues that by structuring our lives to increase daily exposure to diversity, we can foster a more inclusive society. The basis of this suggestion is supported by extensive research. **It is true that intergroup contact can alleviate fears, foster empathy, reduce perceived threats, and shift social norms toward more positive attitudes.**

However, entrenched prejudices, economic disparities, and social inertia can pose significant barriers to this vision. To encourage such decisions, it might be necessary to implement well-designed public policies providing clear and tangible incentives. While some families may be willing to embrace this approach, **expecting widespread voluntary action without adequate structural support may be overly optimistic.**

By addressing these questions, future research can build on Lamont's foundational work, contributing to a deeper understanding of how recognition can continue to evolve and strengthen our capacity to live better together. This potential for further exploration highlights the depth and significance of Lamont's contributions. However, the value of *Seeing Others* lies **not only in its avenues for future research or its moral insights but also, and importantly, in its accessibility to a broader audience.**

Unlike much academic research that is primarily directed at other scholars, Lamont's book is crafted to be understood by a wider readership. **Her ability to engage with complex topics is reflected in the remarkable clarity of her writing.** Without overwhelming the reader with dense academic theories, she elegantly navigates various intellectual perspectives.

Seeing Others transcends academia, **radiating hope and empathy**. Michèle Lamont has indeed crafted a beautiful, powerful, and necessary book.

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